

HEROIC HEARTS: STORY OF COMPASSION AND SELFLESSNESS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of learning how to care for the poor and share what you have. The meaning and relevance of these qualities today is shown through the analysis of the story “The Happy Prince” written by the famous Irish writer Oscar Wilde of the 19th century. While going into detail about how “The Happy Prince” helped the townspeople, the financial situation of the people of that time and their horizons were revealed through analysis of the extracts taken from the literary piece.

Key words: impact, horizon, generosity, loyalty, selflessness, compassion, symbolization, societal indifference.

Introduction: Oscar Wilde, who had left an indelible mark on English literature with his thought-provoking works, poems and dramas, was a man of great talent. Known for his biting wit, and a plentitude of aphorisms, he became one of the most successful playwrights of the late Victorian era in London, and one of the greatest celebrities of his day. [3] He is also the author of numerous short stories. From “The Happy Prince”, a tender story about friendship, compassion, and the transforming power of selfless love, to “The Remarkable Rocket”, a cautionary tale about a deluded, self-important firework, Wilde’s aesthetic preoccupations are evident in every line. [3] Indeed, his unique talent is held

precious not only in the number of stories he wrote, but also in the contemporary relevance of the ideas, themes and events depicted in them.

Literature review: Oscar Wilde was able not only to continue his dramas, plays but also to draw directly from his earlier, non-theatrical works, especially his stories for children and there are clear parallels also. For example, themes like self-sacrifice and forgiveness are of great part in both his social comedies and these stories. In the short story “The Nightingale and the Rose”, a nightingale gives up her life to create a perfect out-of-season red rose for a young man to give to his love, but the sacrifice is unrecognized, the gift is unsuccessful and the rose ends in the gutter. As with “Lady Windermere’s Fan” and “A Woman of No Importance”, some of these stories for children have clear Christian messages. [5.59]

Most of his masterpieces are related to important moral concepts and principles, which are valuable for humanity even today. For instance, in his short story “The Selfish Giant” appeared in the collection called “The Happy Prince and Other Tales” the author wants to tell that “Good people always win. Both in this world and in the Heaven. Being a good person is accepted and important both socially and religiously. It also reflects that sharing our belongings with others is of great importance. [6.13]

In another literary work called “The Devoted Friend” eternal theme of friendship between heroes of the story was skillfully revealed. This short story is about true friendship, and how, as the old adage has it, actions speak louder than words when it comes to demonstrating our devotion to our friends. “The Happy Prince” is also one of the best stories of the author; the motif is devoted to the role of compassion and selflessness on the people. In “The Happy Prince”, the statue of the prince asks a friendly swallow to strip him of his gold leaf and jewels and use them to help the poor. They are both destroyed by their acts of charity, as the swallow dies after missing his chance to migrate and the prince is melted down

because he is no longer beautiful. They are discarded on earth, but Wilde has them both recognized and rewarded by God, spending eternity in paradise.

The story "The Happy Prince" that is included in the collection "The Happy Prince and Other Tales" was published in May 1888, then in 1995, January 1st, Dutton Juvenile republished it and titled the book just "The Happy Prince". Firstly, in terms of the title, in this story the prince was happy when he was alive, as it is stated by him while he was having a conversation with the little swallow:

"Who are you?" the swallow said.

"I'm the Happy Prince."

"Why are you weeping then?" asked the swallow, "you have quite drenched me."

"When I was alive and had a human heart", answered the statue, "I didn't know what tears were, for I lived in the palace of Sans-Souci, where sorrow is not allowed to enter."

But we can learn from the story that, not only was he happy when he was alive, but he was also happy to help people when he became a statue after his death. Also, the poor people at that time could easily get out of difficulties because of the help of the prince.

Research methodology: It is believed that among all his brilliant short stories "The Happy Prince" is considered to be the most famous one which argues that sacrifice, selflessness, love and compassion are the most important things in relationship with people who are in need. This story is shining example of Oscar Wilde's moral stories and in the researches of many critics its literary esteem has been proven.

The main emphasis in this article is given to the analysis of the themes presented in the story, the moral lessons the author wanted to teach us and the help and influence of the statue "The Happy Prince" on the inhabitants of the city.

So, how the themes such as compassion, sacrifice, being judgmental, poverty and wealth are described in the short story? What are the true meanings of the words compassion and sacrifice? How did the happy prince affect the townspeople? For finding answers to these questions, we have tried to investigate some sources.

In Oxford dictionary the word “compassion” is defined as a strong feeling of sympathy for people or animals who are suffering and a desire to help them while the word “sacrifice” means the fact of giving up something important or valuable to you in order to get or do something that seems more important. These two qualities were the main characteristics of the prince as he preferred to help the people who were suffering in his country rather than himself.

Furthermore, the purpose of mentioning the themes of poverty and wealth in this story is that riches are no good if they are not used to help the poor. In addition, depiction of judging others presents the following moral: judge people based on the kindness of their actions not on their appearance. Another theme that was illustrated in the story is sacrifice. We can see the sacrificial giving of both the Happy Prince and the swallow. The prince has gifted his precious stones and even his eyes for the poor’s sake while the swallow has sacrificed his travel plans and, ultimately, his life in order to help the prince. We know that, the prince gives everything he has to give, to show his love and compassion for the people who need it most. At last, but not least, his selfless act of kindness inspires the townspeople to be more compassionate and giving towards one another.

Analysis and results: Any literary discussion will certainly not be true without interpretation of the extracts and passages taken from the book where the essence is revealed. The influence of the statue on people is more certain with the passages below:

“Far away in a little street there is a poor house.... In a bed in the corner of the room seamstress’s little boy is lying ill. He has a fever, and is asking for

oranges. His mother has nothing to give him but river water, so he is crying. Swallow, Swallow, little Swallow, will you not bring her the ruby out of my sword-hilt?"

From this passage we realize that, due to the prince's kindness, the poor family's living condition will certainly get better and the child will also achieve his dream, though it is not directly mentioned in the story. As it is said that, helping one person might not change the world, but it could change the world for one person. Another day the prince helped a young man who was trying to finish a play for the Director of the Theatre. But he was too cold to write anymore because there was no fire in the grate and hunger has made him faint. The prince sent another ruby with the help of the swallow and as a result, this young man was able to finish his work and was never hungry, as it was stated by himself:

"I am beginning to be appreciated", he cried; "this is from some great admirer. Now I can finish my play" and he looked quite happy.

Here the prince sacrifices his sight in order to help. So, he went on to help the poor by giving a helping hand to the little match-girl. He asked the swallow to pluck out his other eye to help this little girl to bring home some money. As usual, a little match-girl was also happy as she ran home, laughing.

The sentences that cannot fail to have a strong impact on every reader's heart are probably the following:

"I am covered with fine gold", said the prince, "you must take it off, leaf by leaf, and give it to my poor; the living always think that gold can make them happy".

And so did it. With the help of the prince's precious stones, the living conditions of the poor people improved and the majority of the people in that town became happy.

In conclusion, the prince's and the swallow's sacrifices are rewarded as they are carried away to Heaven by angels who deem them to be "the two most precious

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things in the city". And we can say that, the statue's generosity serves as a reminder to the townspeople that even in times of hardship, there is always an opportunity to help others and make a positive impact on the world.

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